

LINGUO-COGNITIVE FEATURES OF PUZZLES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *Puzzles are a popular and challenging activity for young children and adults alike. At all ages, puzzles provide the chance to work towards a goal and, literally, put together the pieces of a story or narrative. With fun shapes and bright colours, large-piece puzzles are a favorite among small children, but they also offer an array of developmental benefits so children can learn new skills while they play. In this way, cognitive learning is characterized by comprehension, organizing ideas and applying knowledge through choice and evaluation. When children play with puzzles, they learn the power of choice and strategy as they begin to recognize and thoughtfully understand how pieces fit together to complete a larger picture. Children's puzzles display themes and colorful pictures such as zoo animals, vehicles, numbers or alphabet letters. Playing with puzzles helps them to better understand how themes work together and fit into the world around them.*

Key words: *linguocognitive, puzzle, riddle, jigsaw, comprehension, intellectual potential, mental ability, metaphor.*

The invaluable wealth of our people, the centuries-old way of life passed down from ancestors to generations, the puzzles and riddles have a special place among the examples of oral creativity of the people. In puzzles, people's dreams, hopes, attitudes to events, the world of imagination, and most importantly, the analysis of reality lies in observation and reflection. Riddles are, of course, a spiritual heritage that reflects the historical culture and spirituality of a people. In folklore, various puzzles and riddles are created with the help of figurative expressions, the name of which is kept secret. Finding the answer to riddles encourages a person to think more broadly, to work mentally. A person expands his/her knowledge through thinking on the basis of various sources, information, and enriches

his/ her intellectual potential. Intellectual potential develops in the form of a gradually acquired, developed knowledge complex.

We all know that in order to ensure the quality of foreign language teaching to the younger generation at all stages of the system of continuing education, to radically improve the system of training specialists who are fluent in foreign languages, and to provide similar tasks, decisions and decrees were developed. Taking into account the attention and demand for the study of foreign languages, the analysis of English and Uzbek riddles , their general and specific aspects is an urgent task nowadays. The fact that English is now introduced in the education system from the 1st grade is a proof of the great importance attached to the teaching of this language. Riddles are mainly a means of educating children to increase their vocabulary, expand their understanding and reasoning of concepts and ideas about life and its events. At the same time, the puzzle is not only fun but also a means of developing mental abilities. It is a genre of folk poetry that is unique to all ethnic groups of the world. The riddles are intelligent, poetic, and mostly contain a moral idea. Accordingly, they affect mental, aesthetic, and moral upbringing. In ancient times, they probably packed this feature more or less fulfilled. However, lately, mental education became the main principle in them.

Accordingly, the puzzles are designed to develop children's thinking, teaching them to analyze reality and things and events in different areas of life. Therefore, the presence of many riddles about the same event made it possible to give detailed data about the object (event). Yet, the significance of riddles in mental education does not end with the development of thinking and they enrich knowledge about nature and various spheres of human life. The importance of the use of riddles in mental education is that information about nature and human society is obtained in the process of active mental activity of the child.

It should be highlighted that the main purpose of riddles is to develop thinking and memory as well as to enrich the mind with knowledge. In addition, riddles are enriched with knowledge that helps to form children's minds, other personal characteristics of the mind of a child who knew riddles was enriched not only with intelligent thoughts, but also with kind, beautiful thoughts, and so on .

The most interesting aspects of the work are described in puzzles about labor tools, agricultural crops, pets, clothing, food, etc. Even in fairy tales about the universe, the subject of tools and labor is always present. For example,

The black man dismounted, his children ran. (Pot and dishes)

I have a hundred legs, but cannot stand. I have a long neck, but no head. I can't see, and I help keep your house neat and tidy. What am I? (Broom)

Usually, independent puzzles about a part of an object do not repeat the characters mentioned in the puzzle about the whole object. Such a multifaceted approach to the same topics has helped to develop creative thinking in children, depending on the interaction of its parts.

Two mothers are to five children. (fingers)

Everyone has a horse. (die)

*A son, a mother's child, yet no one's son.
(A girl or daughter)*

Like Uzbek puzzles, English puzzles help to develop figurative associative thinking, ingenuity and logic. English riddle rights to a literary origin, even though this fact is the so-called jigsaw puzzle jigsaw puzzle can be questioned because of their modern form. The English riddle usually appeared in poetic form in old English poetry or in old English literature. The oldest English-language book manuscript (Exeter) associated with the old English puzzles.

The Uzbek puzzle still remains an independent folklore genre. For this reason, the word riddle of the Uzbek and English puzzles for any event or object description given it serious thought is required for identification. In the riddles of all people, the oldest and most common form of "verbal concealment" of well-known notions about objects is a metaphor based on the transfer of similar features from one subject to another. This feature is the structure of the jigsaw as the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle said. He called a riddle as a good metaphor. Many Uzbek riddles are also based on metaphorical descriptions of objects or events: "The white tablecloth covered the earth" (snow), "Between the two lights I am alone in the middle" (nose), "The black cow conquered the whole field" (plowman) and others.

By comparison, there are some examples of English metaphorical riddles: "What is always coming but never arrives?" (tomorrow), "What is broken when you name it?" (silence), "What lives on its own substance and dies when it devours itself?" (a candle), "What is it that you must keep after giving it to someone else?" (a word), "What increases the more you share it with others?" (place).

Well-known scientists engaged in the study of Uzbek folk riddles: Z. Husainova, Z. Razzokov, O. Safarov, O. Imamov and others. However,

English riddles are little learned. They are not a part of English folklore, but, perhaps, a part of the old English poetry.

Thus, the jigsaw puzzle, and in English or the Uzbek language can be united, regardless of their purpose and they contribute to the educational and mental development of human nature. Therefore, riddles are studied in school.

Besides that, history has shown that it appeared at the same time as human civilization. This genre, which has developed and refined over the centuries, has been enriched and studied by both the English and Uzbek people. In this article while analyzing the riddles and puzzles related to household items, we witnessed the commonalities and peculiarities of this field in both languages . In the course of our research, we came to the following conclusions. English riddles are mostly written in prose and modern riddles are common. Basically, puzzles are often used in household objects. On the other hand, riddles in the Uzbek language are found mainly in the form of poetry, rarely in prose and traditional riddles are the majority. Due to its poetic form, it has the characteristics of a poem, but does not always have weight and radiance, there is a type of one- and multi-component riddles. Furthermore, puzzles can stimulate student's mind through helping them improve cognitive activities.

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